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Supplementary Materials for eLetter by Fergus Green,
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**In relation to Fergus Green *et al.* No new fossil fuel projects: The
norm we need, *Science* 384, 954 (2024) DOI: 10.1126/science.adn6533**

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The PDF file includes:

Supplementary methods: Indexing upstream oil production

Supplementary results: Fig. SM.1

Methods: Upstream oil production indexed to 2020 base year

Modellers and data providers tend to use different conversion factors to estimate the energy content of volumetric oil and gas figures reported by the industry. In our original article, we used the production forecast for existing oil and gas fields generated by Rystad Energy, due to their high granularity dataset and overall robust reporting based on company and government data. However, other data providers and modellers make different estimates of oil and gas production measured in energy units.

To test whether differing volume-to-energy conversion rates could affect our oil findings, we have repeated our analysis with indexed projections of both production from existing fields and demand in the selected scenarios, as a proportion of their values in a base year of 2020 (Rystad Energy, 2026a). For the forecasted oil production, we replaced the 2020 and 2021 values with the average of 2019 and 2022 to correct for the COVID pandemic anomaly (most of the scenarios, which were produced in 2020 or earlier, do not need correction) (Rystad Energy 2026b).

As seen in Figure SM.1, below, the median of the 26 selected IPCC C1 mitigation pathways and the 65th percentile still falls well within the level of forecasted oil supply until 2040.

Figure SM.1. Indexed forecast global primary energy production for oil and oil demand in selected IPCC C1 mitigation pathways

Overall, the indexed analysis confirms that our conclusions are not sensitive to assumptions about volume-to-energy conversion factors used by different data providers. Expressing both projected oil production from existing fields and scenario-based demand trajectories relative to a common 2020 baseline yields qualitatively similar results to the primary analysis in absolute energy terms. This robustness check indicates that methodological differences in conversion assumptions do not materially affect the finding published in the original article.

References:

1. Rystad Energy (2026a). UCubeArchive v.2023.09.06
2. Rystad Energy (2026b). UCube v.2026.01.13